

RECENT WORK ON STITCHING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES - THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTS

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SUMMARY: One major problem with resin-based advanced fibre composites is their sensitivity to impact-induced mechanical damage at the interfaces between the laminated plies. Such delamination damage extends under subsequent applications of external load, and causes the laminate to lose much of its original strength. A simple way to combat this problem is to improve delamination crack-growth resistance by means of through-thickness reinforcement in the form of transverse stitching. Although stitching may lead to a significant improvement in the delamination crack-growth resistance, at the same time it may degrade the in-plane mechanical properties due to the creation of resin pockets or the breakage of in-plane fibres. This paper presents the effect of stitching on interlaminar as well as in-plane properties. The sample composite components were fabricated from unidirectional pre-preg tape as well as from dry carbon fabric and resin using resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique. The stitching was performed with the Kevlar thread. The effect of stitching on the degradation of in-plane mechanical properties was found to be negligible. The mode I toughness improved by up to ten times and the mode II toughness three times. The effects of various parameters such as stitch density, stitch-thread diameter were examined. In addition, a comparison with the micromechanics-based models developed by Jain and Mai [1,2] to predict the mode I and mode II delamination toughness is provided and good agreement is found between theoretical predictions and experimental data.

KEYWORDS: through-thickness reinforcement, stitching, delamination, mechanical properties, mode I and mode II fracture toughness, modelling.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced composite laminates have a considerable advantage over traditional engineering materials in weight-critical applications. However, due to their low interlaminar fracture toughness, these laminates are susceptible to delamination when subjected to interlaminar stress concentrations. Interlaminar stresses may arise from manufacturing defects such as air entrapment or regions of insufficient resin, low velocity impact or geometric discontinuities such as free edges, notches, ply terminations, and bolted and bonded joints [3]. In some circumstances, this may lead simply to a substantial decrease in the structural integrity whilst in others it may be responsible for the catastrophic failure of the component.

There are two methods by which the damage tolerance of a composite structure can be improved. The first involves material selection and focuses on the use of tougher matrices, better fibre/matrix interfaces, fibre hybridisation and interleaving concepts [4-6]. These techniques, with the exception of interleaving, generally only lead to minor improvements in the delamination resistance [7,8]. The second method utilises existing textile technologies such as stitching, knitting, weaving or braiding to introduce through-thickness fibre reinforcement into the laminate. [7,9-20].

Textile fibre geometries which have through-thickness reinforcement are called three-dimensional (3D) fabrics. The fabrication of a fabric using knitting, weaving or braiding can be done in a one-step process with the z-direction fibres being introduced simultaneously. Damage to the in-plane fibres can therefore be avoided. Stitching, on the other hand, requires at least one additional step with the through-thickness fibres being introduced after the layup of the laminate and the sewing process is responsible for an amount of in-plane fibre damage. However, whilst a considerable improvement in the mode I fracture toughness is possible with weaving, knitting and braiding, these methods create large resin pockets throughout the structure and thus reduce the volume fraction of the in-plane fibres, compared to an analogous two-dimensional (2D) laminate, which results in a large decrease in the in-plane properties. Perhaps the biggest advantage of stitching compared to the other methods of through-thickness reinforcement is its versatility. Stitching utilises traditional materials and fabrication processes and components can be manufactured from either a prepreg or preform layup. In addition stitching can be used in composite joining instead of more traditional mechanical or adhesive techniques [21,22].

In this study, the composite specimens were fabricated from dry fabric and resin using resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique and from unidirectional prepreg tape. The stitching process degrades the in-plane mechanical properties (such as stiffness, strength, etc.) due to the formation of resin-rich pockets near the stitching loops or due to the breakage of in-plane fibres. The in-plane properties of the stitched laminates were determined experimentally and then compared with those of the unstitched laminates. The effect of stitching on mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was determined using the double cantilever beam (DCB) test and on mode II interlaminar fracture toughness using the end-notched flexure (ENF) test (see Figures 1 and 2). During the mode I testing of RTM specimens, the stitched specimens exhibited failure of a cantilever in bending rather than self-similar crack propagation between the plies. Therefore, a new DCB specimen configuration based on the design developed by Guenon et al. [9] was consequently used. This specimen, termed the tabbed DCB (TDCB), utilises long aluminium tabs bonded along the specimen length to prevent failure of the composite cantilevers (Figure 1). These reinforcing tabs may alter the failure mechanisms of the stitching thread and thus may have an effect on the improvement in mode I delamination toughness. Therefore, to examine the effect of the reinforcing tabs on the mode I toughness, the prepreg samples were tested with and without the tabs. The mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughnesses of stitched laminates were compared with those of unstitched laminates having similar material system and in-plane stacking sequence.

In addition, the steady state delamination toughness of stitched RTM specimens was compared with that of stitched prepreg specimens. Experimental data were finally compared with theoretical predictions based on micromechanics models developed by Jain and Mai [1,2].

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of (a) untabbed specimen and (b) tabbed specimen for mode I indicating specimen and tab dimensions.

Fig. 2: End-notched flexure specimen geometry.

MATERIAL SYSTEMS

Specimen Manufacture

Carbon/epoxy RTM panels with mid-plane inserts were fabricated from Ciba-Geigy "uniweave" Injectex fabric and GY260 resin. "Uniweave" fabric consists of a large percentage of 3K tow carbon warp yarns (in this case 90% by weight) held together by 1K tow carbon fill yarns in the weft direction. Following the stacking, some of the dry fabric lay-ups were stitched through-the-thickness at 90° to the warp direction. Modified lock stitch was employed to avoid the disruption to the laminate arising from any interior looping process between the bobbin and needle threads. The through-thickness reinforcement penetrated the in-plane yarns hence some fibre breakage and misalignment occurred at each stitching needle penetration. The advent of fibre damage and misalignment resulted in the formation of resin rich pockets around the thread. The ply orientation of both the unstitched and stitched materials were essentially unidirectional. All the dry fibre preforms were infiltrated with the GY260 epoxy resin in conjunction with HY917 hardener and DY070 accelerator with 100, 90 and 1 weight proportions, respectively. The laminates were cured for 4 hours at 80 °C and then postcured for 4 hours at 160 °C.

The prepreg samples were fabricated from Ciba-Geigy aerospace grade 913 prepreg and ICI Fiberite 948 prepreg tapes. To enable direct comparison with RTM specimens, the lay-up was kept unidirectional. Prior to curing the laminates, stitching was performed with a domestic sewing machine. The cure cycles recommended by the manufacturer were employed. For the 948 system, the layup was first heated from room temperature to 80°C at a rate of 2°C/min. This temperature was held for 15 minutes. The temperature was subsequently raised at a rate of 2°C/min to 121°C and this temperature was held for 120 minutes. Cooling at a rate of 2°C/min followed. An external pressure of 7 atmosphere and a vacuum of 1 atmosphere was applied throughout the procedure. For the 913 system, cure cycle consisted of four hours at 120°C with a differential pressure of 4 atmospheres. The differential pressure consisted of 1 atmosphere of vacuum and 3 atmospheres of external pressure.

All test coupons were 14 plies thick. The average specimen thickness for both the stitched and unstitched materials was 2.97 mm. The mid-plane delamination was introduced during the layup by means of a 0.012 mm thick Teflon strip inserted between the 7th and 8th plies. All specimens were milled after the cutting procedure to ensure a consistent cross-section and to eliminate any damage.

Stitching Yarns

The stitching was performed with the commercially available K40, K60 and K80 Kevlar® threads. The terms K40, K60 and K80 represent 40 Tex (2 ply), 60 Tex (3 ply) and 80 Tex (3 ply) sewing threads, respectively. The tensile strength and modulus of the threads were evaluated as per ASTM D2256-81 and D3379-75. Under mode I loading failure of the thread was predominantly at the needle/bobbin thread intersection. Thus the intersection was imitated using a "loop" configuration (ASTM D3217-79) and the thread strength was determined both prior to and after the stitching process. Each result was determined from 16-20 tests using a Weibull data reduction method. The results are presented in Table 1. Further details on the test methods and data reduction method may be found in Ref. [20].

The use of the theoretical models [1] required a knowledge of the thread/matrix interfacial shear stress. The interfacial properties were determined using a novel pull-out test where the

thread was pulled from a composite laminate. The interfacial properties of the thread pull-out test are also presented in Table 1.

A summary of the stitching variables studied and the fibre volume fraction for the various laminates is presented in Table 2. The term discontinuous in this table refers to the laminates where the surface loops are removed by grinding the top and the bottom parts.

IN-PLANE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Stitching of preforms or prepregs causes stress concentrations and damage to the in-plane fibres and hence degrades the in-plane mechanical properties. The Young's modulus, flexural modulus, failure strength, and shear strength of stitched laminates were determined experimentally for some of the laminates and are summarised below. In determining these properties, the transverse shear modulus, where required, was assumed to be 5.8 GPa.

The tensile and compressive properties were determined by loading the specimen in uniaxial tension and compression, respectively. These tests were carried out on rectangular coupons of 160 mm in length, 15 mm in width and 3 mm in thickness as per ASTM standard. For the tensile test specimens, at each end, 40 mm of the specimen was held in the grips, leaving a test area of 80 x 15 mm². To prevent failure in the grips, it was also necessary to employ aluminium tabs in the case of longitudinal tension specimens. However, no tabbing was required while performing the test in the transverse direction. The compressive test specimen had a test area of 10 x 15 mm² with 70 mm held in the grips at both ends (in an IITRI test fixture). The measurement of the Young's modulus and failure strain were facilitated by the use of a centrally located strain gauge. The strain gauge data was directly fed into a 486 PC data logger. The load was applied by a screw driven Instron 1195 using a 100KN load cell. The self-tightening wedge action grips were used to introduce the load to the specimen. An increasing load was applied to the specimen at a uniform displacement rate of 1 mm/min until fracture of the specimen occurred. The load, displacement, time and strain were constantly recorded using a 486 PC data logger throughout the test. For each variable four to six specimens were tested. The load-displacement curves were essentially linear until fracture occurred. The strength was determined from the failure load and the Young's modulus was determined from the gradient of the linear (elastic) portion of the stress-strain curve. The results for the longitudinal and transverse tensile properties and compressive properties are summarised in Tables 3-5.

It can be seen from Tables 3 and 5 that the longitudinal Young's modulus and tensile and compressive strengths reduce by up to 15% due to the in-plane fibre damage and stress concentrations caused by the stitches. However, reduction in these properties is quite insignificant compared to the improvements achieved in the delamination toughness. In most cases, the failure of the specimen was caused by crack initiation at the stitch line. To examine the effect of surface in-plane waviness caused by the stitching loops, the top and the bottom surfaces of the CRC-AS K40 4 st/cm² laminate were ground off. These samples are designated as CRC-AS K40 4 st/cm² "discontinuous" stitched samples. These specimens exhibited an apparent increase in strength and a reduction in stiffness in tension. However, in compression, a reduction in strength and an increase in stiffness was found. Table 4 shows that stitching did not affect the transverse tensile properties. It should be noted here that the transverse modulus and strengths of RTM specimens is much larger than that of pre-preg specimens because of 10% carbon fill yarns in the weft direction.

Table 1 Fibre and Thread Tensile Properties [20].

	Single Fibre			Prior to stitching			After stitching			Pull-out shear stress τ (MPa)
	Tensile			Tensile			Tensile			
	σ_m (GPa)	E_f (GPa)	σ_m (GPa)	E_f (GPa)	Loop σ_m (GPa)	σ_m (GPa)	E_f (GPa)	Loop σ_m (GPa)		
2-ply Kevlar	3.20	124	2.82	76.3	2.10	2.05	62.5	1.79	18.2	
3-ply Kevlar	3.20	124	2.65	66.8	2.15	2.09	56.8	1.89	21.4	
4-ply Kevlar	3.20	124	2.59	57.8	2.21	2.14	49.3	1.87	24.7	

Table 2: Materials studied, stitch variables and average fibre volume fraction [20].

Material	Thread Type	Stitch density (stitches/cm ²)	Stitch Pitch	Stitch Line Spacing	Volume Fraction (%)
RTM	-	Unstitched	-	-	58.0
RTM	2 ply Kevlar	4	3.40 mm	7.5 mm	58.6
RTM	2 ply Kevlar	4 (discontinuous stitch)	3.40 mm	7.5 mm	60.5
RTM	2 ply Kevlar	8	3.40 mm	3.35 mm	58.6
RTM	2 ply Kevlar	12	3.25 mm	2.6 mm	57.6
RTM	3 ply Kevlar	4	3.40 mm	7.5 mm	58.8
RTM	4 ply Kevlar	4	3.40 mm	7.5 mm	57.4
RTM	4 ply Kevlar	8	3.40 mm	3.35 mm	58.0
948	-	unstitched	-	-	63.5
948	2 ply Kevlar	4	3.12 mm	6.9 mm	63.4
913	-	unstitched	-	-	64.7
913	2 ply Kevlar	2	3.12 mm	14.0 mm	64.1
913	2 ply Kevlar	4	3.12mm	6.9 mm	64.5
913	2 ply Kevlar	4 (discontinuous stitch)	3.12mm	6.9 mm	66.3

Table 3: Effect of stitching on longitudinal tensile properties.

Material	Thread type and stitch density	Failure strength σ_m (GPa)	Young's Modulus E_{11} (GPa)
RTM	unstitched	1.20 ± 0.01	106.3 ± 0.5
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	1.19 ± 0.05	105.3 ± 11
RTM	2-ply K 8 st/cm ²	1.15 ± 0.02	105.8 ± 1.8
RTM	3-ply K 4 st/cm ²	1.02 ± 0.01	103.3 ± 2.3
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ² (1)	1.27 ± 0.06	91.5 ± 2.5
948	unstitched	1.55 ± 0.04	119.3 ± 2.3
948	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	1.43 ± 0.03	127.6 ± 2.0
913	unstitched	1.39 ± 0.03	126.7 ± 1.0
913	2-ply K 2 st/cm ²	1.16 ± 0.02	121.2 ± 1.3
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	1.18 ± 0.01	122.2 ± 0.7
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ² (1)	1.38 ± 0.01	110.9 ± 8.5

K - Kevlar, (1) - discontinuous stitch

Table 4: Effect of stitching on transverse tensile properties.

Material	Thread type and stitch density	Failure strength σ_m (MPa)	Young's modulus E_{22} (GPa)
RTM	unstitched	164.2 ± 5.7	36.0 ± 0.8
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	157.8 ± 1.1	36.5 ± 0.1
913	unstitched	82.3 ± 2.3	8.7 ± 0.5
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	83.4 ± 3.1	8.5 ± 0.4

K - Kevlar

Table 5: Effect of stitching on compressive properties.

Material	Thread type and stitch density	Failure strength σ_m (MPa)	Young's Modulus E_{11} (GPa)
RTM	unstitched	472.2 ± 10.2	99.8 ± 0.3
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	406.2 ± 15.3	113.4 ± 1.6
RTM	2-ply K 8 st/cm ²	403.3 ± 25.8	104.3 ± 3.1
RTM	3-ply K 4 st/cm ²	398.7 ± 12.9	108.7 ± 7.6
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ² (1)	416.2 ± 12.6	107.9 ± 5.3
948	unstitched	708.0 ± 32.6	111.8 ± 3.5
948	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	614.1 ± 25.4	102.2 ± 4.8
913	unstitched	713.1 ± 18.3	117.8 ± 2.8
913	2-ply K 2 st/cm ²	643.3 ± 15.4	112.1 ± 3.5
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	632.6 ± 30.2	105.3 ± 4.2
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ² (1)	658.5 ± 12.8	112.4 ± 1.7

K - Kevlar, (1) - discontinuous stitch

The composite interlaminar shear specimens were 33 mm in length, 6.5 mm in width and 3 mm in thickness. The interlaminar shear strength properties were determined using the short beam shear test (ASTM standard D2344). This test utilises a three-point bending fixture of 25 mm gauge length. The compressive load was applied through a servo-hydraulic Instron 4302 material testing machine using a 10KN load cell. A uniform displacement rate of 5 mm/min was used until an interlaminar crack appeared in the specimen. The specimens were very rate sensitive with rates of 1 and 2 mm/min producing compressive failure under the central loading pin rather than interlaminar failure. The load, displacement and time were continuously recorded using a 286 PC data logger. The load increased linearly until the interlaminar crack was observed. This interlaminar crack tended to extend from the central loading pin to the specimen end in the unstitched specimen, and from the central loading pin to the nearest stitch line in the stitched specimen. For each variable six specimens were tested. The interlaminar shear strength was obtained from the following expression:

$$\tau_s = \frac{3P}{8wh_c} \quad (1)$$

where P is the failure load, w is the width of the specimen and h_c is the half-beam thickness. The results are presented in Table 6. It can be seen from this table that the effect of stitching on the interlaminar shear strength is negligible.

Table 6: Effect of stitching on interlaminar shear strength.

Material	Thread type and stitch density	Shear strength τ_s (MPa)
RTM	unstitched	51.64 ± 1.23
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	51.02 ± 2.41
RTM	2-ply K 4 st/cm ² (1)	50.92 ± 0.94
RTM	2-ply K 8 st/cm ²	51.52 ± 1.15
RTM	3-ply K 4 st/cm ²	50.40 ± 1.97
948	unstitched	57.3 ± 2.70
948	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	57.5 ± 4.24
913	unstitched	59.5 ± 2.08
913	2-ply K 2 st/cm ²	57.9 ± 0.87
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ²	62.0 ± 2.41
913	2-ply K 4 st/cm ² (1)	48.9 ± 1.56

K - Kevlar, (1) - discontinuous stitch

MODE I DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS

Experimental Technique

The standard double-cantilever-beam (DCB) test is ideal to determine the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. This test utilises specimens of 3 mm thickness, 25 mm width and 150 mm in length. The specimens were manufactured so that the crack length from the loading point to the crack tip was 25 mm.

The load was applied through the use of aluminium T-tabs fixed to the specimen end containing the delamination (Figure 1). This methodology was found to be adequate with the unstitched RTM and both stitched and unstitched prepreg specimens. However, as mentioned earlier, when the stitched RTM specimens were tested, failure of a cantilever in bending rather than self-similar crack propagation between the plies occurred. Therefore, tabbed DCB (TDCB) specimens based on the design developed by Guenon et al. [9] were consequently used. This specimen configuration utilises long aluminium tabs bonded along the specimen length to prevent failure of the composite cantilevers (Figure 1). To prevent the yielding of the long aluminium tabs, a minimum thickness of 6 mm is required for the tabs. However, readily available 10 mm thick aluminium tabs were used. To examine the effect of these reinforcing tabs, stitched prepreg specimens were tested both with and without tabs. To ensure consistency with the results and to help identify failure mechanisms associated with the stitches, unstitched specimens were also tested both with and without the long aluminium tabs.

For load application T-tabs were fixed to the long aluminium tabs using both adhesive and bolts. Following the specimen manufacture, a razor blade was used to wedge open the initial delamination to form a sharp mode I precrack. The sides of the specimen were coated with a thin layer of white correction fluid to aid measurement of the initial crack length and to assist visual observation of the crack propagation during the test. Subsequently, the DCB specimens, both untabbed and tabbed, were pin loaded in tension using Instron grips in a servohydraulic Instron 4302 materials testing machine. A 10 KN load cell was employed to apply the load to the specimen through the fixture and T-tab. Displacement control mode was used with a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. A data logger was used to continuously record the load, displacement and time. A travelling microscope with a light source enabled visual examination of the specimen throughout the test and measurement of the crack length.

The specimen was loaded until the crack propagated several millimetres. The specimen was then unloaded and the crack tip marked. This process was repeated 10-15 times for each specimen. The crack lengths, defined as the distance from the loading point to the crack tip, were measured using the travelling microscope. For each variable four to six specimens were tested.

Analysis

The interlaminar fracture toughness was determined in terms of the mode I critical energy release rate, G_{IR} (which may be regarded as G_{IC} in the case of unstitched laminates with no R-curve behaviour), using the direct method. This method requires information on the crack propagation load as a function of crack length which was determined using the data logger and the travelling microscope.

The mode I critical energy release rate, G_{IR} , as defined by the Griffith's energetic fracture criterion, is given by [1]

$$G_{IR} = \frac{P^2}{w} \left[\frac{(a + \chi h_c)^2}{E_c I_c} + \frac{6}{5 G_{12c} h_c w} \right] \quad (2)$$

where P is the applied load, a is the crack length, E_c is the flexural modulus of the composite, $E_c I_c$ is the flexural rigidity, w is the beam width, h_c is the beam thickness and G_{12c} is the transverse shear modulus. χ is a correction factor which takes into account the additional

deflection due to rotation of the beams and is equal to 0.6 [23]. The two terms on the right hand side of the equation are the contributions from bending and shear deflections, respectively. From equation (2) it is possible to determine a set of mode I energy release rate values, G_{IR} , as a function of crack growth, Δa , if the crack propagation load is known. To account for the long aluminium tabs required by the stitched RTM DCB specimens, in equation (2), the beam thickness h_c is replaced by $h_c + h_a$ where h_a is the thickness of the aluminium tab. The flexural rigidity $E_c I_c$ is replaced by EI and the shear modulus G_{12c} is replaced by G_{12} for the composite-aluminium beam. The expressions for EI and G_{12} may be found in Ref. [24,25]. In determining flexural rigidity, EI , and the shear modulus, G_{12} , E_a of 6061 aluminium was taken as 68.9 GPa and G_a as 26.9 GPa [26].

Results and Discussion

Observation of the load-displacement curves obtained from stitched specimens (Figure 3) shows that initially there is an increase in the crack propagation load as the crack grows. This is caused by the development of the stitch bridging zone. After the bridging zone is fully developed, the steady-state interlaminar fracture toughness is attained and with further crack propagation the stitches start breaking and the crack propagation load decreases with increasing crack length. The crack propagation part of the curve generally exhibited stable crack propagation behaviour consisting of successive load drops followed by crack arrest. This is termed the "stick-slip" behaviour. In the case of the unstitched specimen, there was a continual decrease in the crack propagation load with increasing crack length for both the untabbed and tabbed samples. The load-displacement curves of the stitched specimen also show an appreciable amount of permanent deformation. The crack opening displacement is non-zero after unloading and observation of the crack tip with the travelling microscope revealed that the crack tip had not closed completely. This was due to the fact that most of the stitches did not break in the plane of the crack. Instead, the stitches fractured at the thread intersection at the outer surface of the composite and subsequently pulled out. The pulled-out stitch loops did not return to their original location during unloading and this led to a non-linear unloading behaviour and a permanent deflection of the specimen after unloading was complete. The R-curves for different material variables were determined. The flexural modulus required to determine these curves are given in Table 7 and the out-of-plane shear modulus was estimated to be 5.8 GPa. The R-curves are shown in Figures 4 and 5. It was immediately obvious that the addition of through-thickness reinforcement by stitching produced a significant improvement in the mode I delamination fracture toughness. To determine the major energy absorption mechanisms responsible for the improvement, delamination surfaces of the stitched specimens were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Evidence of thread breakage and subsequent pull-out was found (Figure 6). Thus it was postulated that several processes were involved in increasing the toughness. Debonding of the thread/matrix interface allowed elastic stretching of the thread. This created fibre bridging of the crack by the stitch lines providing crack closure forces until thread failure and pull-out occurred. The unstitched specimens also exhibited R-curve behaviour (Figures 4-5). This incremental increase in the fracture toughness was due to some fibre bridging effect caused by the in-plane carbon fibres. A study of the fracture surface using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) found some evidence of fibre bridging (Figure 7). The steady-state G_{IRs} values for the unstitched specimens, both tabbed and untabbed, exhibited good agreement for RTM as well as prepreg specimens (see Table 8).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3: Typical load versus displacement plots for (a) an unstitched, tabbed specimen (b) a specimen stitched with K40 thread at 4 st/cm² and (c) a specimen stitched with K80 thread at 8 st/cm².

This indicated that for the unstitched specimens, the addition of long aluminium tabs did not alter the failure mechanisms during the crack propagation. However, a considerable increase in the length of the crack bridging or process zone before attaining steady-state behaviour was observed. The reason for this is that addition of the aluminium tabs has produced a stiffer specimen and thus created a longer crack bridging zone. It can clearly be observed from the R-curves (Figure 4-5) that the crack bridging zone of the unstitched specimens increased from 20-25 mm to 37-42 mm for the RTM specimens and from 20-25 mm to 45-55 mm for 948 and 913 prepreg specimens. The unstitched RTM material exhibited higher toughness compared to the prepreg materials. Amongst the prepreg materials, the tougher, aerospace grade 913 prepreg demonstrated 30% higher toughness compared to the 948 prepreg material.

Table 7 Material and Geometric parameters used in the prediction of G_{IR}

Parameter	RTM						948	913	
	2-ply K			3-ply K	4-ply K		2-ply K	2-ply K	
stitch/cm ²	4	8	12	4	4	8	4	4	8
E_c (GPa)	95.5	88.9	87.5	90.7	89.5	85.6	119.3	121.2	122.2
τ (MPa)	18.2			21.4	24.7		18.2	18.2	
E_0 (GPa)	11.4			11.4	11.4		12.3	12.3	
K_{Ic} (MPa \sqrt{m})	2.24			2.24	2.24		1.8	2.04	
a_0 (mm)	25			25	25		25	25	
h_c (mm)	1.5			1.5	1.5		1.5	1.5	
d_f (mm)	0.16			0.200	0.234		0.16	0.16	
L_p (mm)	3.33			3.33	3.33		3.33	3.33	
S_f (mm)	7.5	3.75	2.5	7.5	7.5	3.75	7.5	15.0	7.5
σ_u (GPa)	1.79			1.89	1.87		1.8	1.8	
E_c (GPa)	62.5			56.8	49.3		62.5	62.5	

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It is reasonable to hypothesise that a larger stitch bridging zone resulting from stiffening the specimen by the addition of tabs would produce higher G_{IRs} values. However, in the case of all stitched prepreg laminates, although a significant increase in the length of the bridging zone was observed after the application of tabs, a 30% reduction in G_{IRs} was found as compared to untabbed specimens (see Table 8). To ascertain possible explanations for this the role of the surface stitch loop must be considered. The G_{IRs} values of continuously stitched specimens prior to and after removal of the surface loop (discontinuous) displayed a loss of 50% for both the 913 prepreg and RTM specimens. Compared to unstitched specimens, a two to three-fold improvement in delamination toughness with discontinuous stitching was still produced. This eventuated from debonding at the thread/matrix interface and subsequent pull-out of the thread. Therefore it may be deduced that the interfacial shear stress at the thread/matrix interface is considerable to provide the crack closure forces. However, in the case of continuous stitching employing the same thread and stitch density, a five to seven fold improvement in the mode I delamination toughness was found. Thus it was concluded that the major contribution to the improvement in toughness transpired from elastic stretching of the stitches prior to thread failure and pull-out.

Having postulated that the elastic stretching of the thread was the major contributing mechanism involved in the improvement in toughness, the toughness must be dependent on the length of thread available to stretch. To analyse this the delaminated surfaces of the

Fig. 4: R-curves for RTM specimens - (a) unstitched, (b) stitched with 2-ply Kevlar thread at 4 st/cm^2 , 8 st/cm^2 , and 12 st/cm^2 and (c) continuous and discontinuous stitches with 2-Ply Kevlar at 4 st/cm^2 . The R-curves for specimens stitched with 3-ply and 4-ply Kevlar threads are similar.

Fig. 5: R-curves for 913 prepreg specimens - (a) unstitched, untabbed and tabbed and (b) stitched with 2-ply Kevlar at 4 st/cm², untabbed and tabbed. The R-curves for 948 prepreg specimens are similar.

Fig. 6: SEM fractograph displaying the failure behaviour under mode I loading of a Kevlar thread. Evidence of debonding, thread failure and pull out may be seen (After [20]).

Fig. 7: SEM fractograph showing fibre bridging of in-plane carbon fibres in an unstitched specimen (After [20]).

Table 8 Mode I toughness determined using the direct method

Specimen			G_{TRC} (KJ/m ²)	Improvement Factor
RTM	unstitched	untabbed	0.41 ± 0.02	-
		tabbed	0.44 ± 0.03	-
RTM	K40 4 st/cm ²	tabbed	2.03 ± 0.04	4.6
RTM	K40 4 st/cm ² (1)	tabbed	0.98 ± 0.09	2.2
RTM	K40 8 st/cm ²	tabbed	2.82 ± 0.09	6.4
RTM	K40 12 st/cm ²	tabbed	4.10 ± 0.25	9.3
RTM	K60 4 st/cm ²	tabbed	2.59 ± 0.11	5.9
RTM	K80 4 st/cm ²	tabbed	2.90 ± 0.12	6.6
RTM	K80 8 st/cm ²	tabbed	4.54 ± 0.10	10.3
948	unstitched	untabbed	0.26 ± 0.012	-
		tabbed	0.28 ± 0.010	-
948	4 stitches/cm ²	untabbed	2.19 ± 0.14	8.4
		tabbed	1.48 ± 0.05	5.2
913	unstitched	untabbed	0.34 ± 0.01	-
		tabbed	0.38 ± 0.02	-
913	2 stitches/cm ²	untabbed	1.56 ± 0.09	4.5
913	4 stitches/cm ²	untabbed	2.44 ± 0.07	7.2
		tabbed	1.64 ± 0.10	4.3
913	4 stitches/cm ² (1)	tabbed	1.13 ± 0.08	3.0

(1) Discontinuous stitch

various stitched specimens were examined using SEM. It was determined that the thread fracture processes consisted similar mechanisms in all specimens, namely (i) thread/matrix interfacial debonding, (ii) elastic stretching of the thread and, (iii) thread failure and pull-out. Examination of the delamination surfaces of the tabbed stitched specimens disclosed failure of the thread at the intersection of the stitch loop and the surface thread (Figure 8). In the case of untabbed specimens, although thread failure at the intersection of the stitch loop and the surface thread occurred, it was obvious from the observation of the surfaces of the stitched specimens that the portion of the thread on the surface also underwent significant stretching. Thus it was concluded that the addition of tabs prevented the surface loop from stretching. This reduced the thread length available for stretching and hence resulted in a decrease in the improvement in mode I delamination toughness.

A summary of the improvement in toughness when compared to the relevant unstitched toughness values is also presented in Table 8. From this table it can also be seen that stitched, tabbed RTM specimens exhibited higher delamination toughness as compared to the stitched, tabbed prepreg specimens. This trend is similar to the one observed for the unstitched specimens.

Fig. 8: SEM fractograph displaying thread loop pull-out failure behaviour under mode I loading of a tabbed, Kevlar thread stitched specimen (After [20]).

Micromechanical Model

Two simple micromechanics-based models using a stress intensity factor approach have been developed by Jain and Mai [1] to predict the effect of stitching on the mode I delamination toughness. In the first model each stitch was considered as an independent (discontinuous) through-thickness reinforcement. In this case, the expression for crack closure traction contained terms for frictional slip and thread pull-out. In the second model, the effect of

interconnected stitching was incorporated. This model utilised terms for frictional slip, elastic stretching, and thread rupture in the crack plane. However, as described above, the thread fracture behaviour of the stitched double cantilever beam specimens was found experimentally to consist of (i) thread debonding (ii) elastic stretching of the thread (iii) thread rupture, and (iv) thread pull-out. These models, therefore, have been modified by Jain et al. [24,25] to accurately account for the various failure mechanisms occurring during the delamination crack propagation. It should also be pointed out here that Mourtiz and Jain [27] found that in the case of 6 mm thick stitched glass reinforced polymer composites, the stitches failed in the crack plane and no stitch thread pull-out was observed.

The assumptions involved in the theoretical models may be found in Ref. [1]. To simulate the failure mechanisms observed in the case of tabbed RTM and prepreg specimens, it was assumed that the effective thread length available for elastic stretching was equal to the laminate thickness ($2h_c$) and that available for pull-out was half the laminate thickness, h_c , as the stitch breaks at one end and then pulls out. In the case of untabbed prepreg specimens, the effect of stitch pitch length, L_p , has to be accounted. Therefore, the stitch length available for elastic stretching was estimated to be $2h_c + L_p$ and that available for pull out was h_c .

From the closure traction $P(t)$ provided by the bridging stitches, the crack growth resistance, K_{IR} , as a function of crack growth, Δa , can be obtained as follows [1]

$$K_{IR}(\Delta a) = K_{Ic} + Y \int_{t=0}^{\Delta a} P(t) \frac{1}{\sqrt{h_c}} f\left(\frac{t}{h_c}\right) dt \quad (3)$$

where K_{Ic} is the initiation fracture toughness of the stitched composite which is taken as the steady state value for the unstitched composite. Inclusion of the matrix R-curve (i.e. matrix process zone) in addition to the fibre bridging zone for fibre cements has been analysed by Cotterell and Mai [28]. The parameter Y is an orthotropic correction factor and $f(t/h_c)$ is a geometric factor [1].

Once the stress intensity $K_{IR}(\Delta a)$ has been determined using equation (3), the fracture toughness in terms of energy release rate, $G_{IR}(\Delta a)$, may be obtained as follows

$$G_{IR}(\Delta a) = \frac{K_{IR}^2(\Delta a)}{E_0} \quad (4)$$

where E_0 is the orthotropic modulus [1].

The material and geometric parametric values of the laminate and thread materials used in the prediction of delamination toughness are given in Table 7. Note that a_0 is the initial crack length and S_L is the stitch line spacing. The value for the initiation fracture toughness of the stitched composite, K_{Ic} , was calculated from the experimentally determined steady-state energy release rate for the unstitched specimens using equation (4).

The theoretical predictions and the experimental results are presented in Figures 9-11. In the case of RTM specimens, comparison between theory and experimental results with increasing stitch density shows good agreement. Likewise for the prepreg materials, the agreement is very good for both tabbed and untabbed specimens.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9: Comparison of experimental results and theoretical predictions showing trend with stitch density for tabbed, RTM specimens for (a) 2-ply Kevlar thread and (b) 4-ply Kevlar thread.

Fig. 10: Comparison of experimental results and theoretical predictions with Kevlar thread diameter for RTM specimens.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11: Comparison of experimental results and theoretical predictions for (a) 948 and (b) 913 tabbed and untabbed prepreg specimens.

MODE II DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS

Experimental Procedure

All mode II tests were performed on end-notched flexure (ENF) specimens using a three point bend fixture (Figure 2). Prior to testing, a mode I precrack was propagated in the specimen by wedging the initial delamination open with a razor blade. This procedure was performed to transform the blunt resin rich crack tip into a sharp one.

As with mode I testing, following the precracking procedure the specimen edges were coated with a thin layer of water soluble correction fluid to enable accurate measurement of the initial crack length and visual observation of the delamination. The specimens were positioned in the three-point bend fixture with a total span of 100 mm so that an initial crack length of 25 mm was achieved. The load was applied to the specimen via the central loading pin by a servo-hydraulic

Instron 4302 in displacement controlled mode. A 10 KN load cell was employed. The cross-head moved at a constant speed of 1 mm/min. A data logger was used to record the load, displacement and time information continuously. A travelling microscope with a light source was employed to observe delamination. The specimens were loaded until crack propagation occurred. In the case of the unstitched specimens this cracking was unstable and continued to the central loading pin instantaneously. The test was then concluded. Crack propagation in stitched, prepreg samples was also unstable. This resulted from the loosening of the stitches due to the compaction during the autoclave processing. The slackening of the stitches was measured to be close to 0.3 mm for the laminates. Thus over a specimen gauge length of 100 mm, which induced a relative sliding between the top and bottom of the specimen of 0.18 mm at the first stitch line, a load would not yet be applied to the bridging threads. Theoretically, if a large enough specimen was tested, stable crack propagation would result subsequent to the thread slackness being taken up by 0.3 mm of relative sliding in the specimen. However, the crack propagation in the stitched, RTM specimens displayed a stable behaviour. Thus after the crack had propagated several millimetres the specimens were unloaded and the crack tip marked. The specimens were subsequently loaded again. This process was repeated several times until the crack had reached the central loading pin. The crack lengths were measured using the travelling microscope.

Analysis

Since the layup of the laminates under study was essentially unidirectional, the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in terms of the energy release rate was determined using the following expression:

$$G_{IIR} = \frac{9}{16} \frac{P^2}{w^2 E_c h_c^3} (a + \alpha h_c)^2 \quad (5)$$

where α is a shear correction factor which depends on the ratio of axial (E_{11}) and out-of-plane shear (G_{12}) stiffnesses of the beam. For unidirectional composites, α can be approximated by [29]

$$\alpha = 0.13 \left(\frac{E_{11}}{G_{12}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

Results and Discussion

Typical load versus deflection curves obtained from testing the stitched and unstitched laminates using the ENF geometry are shown in Figure 12. It can be seen from Figure 12a that the load increases linearly in the case of the unstitched specimen and when the energy release rate exceeds the critical energy release rate, the crack propagates in an unstable manner to the central loading pin, leading to a sudden load drop. In the case of stitched composites, the crack growth was generally stable and initially there was an increase in the crack propagation load with crack growth due to the development of bridging stitch thread zone (see Figure 12b). This leads to an increase in the delamination toughness and hence a rising R-curve. Some unstable crack propagation leading to a sudden load drop and then crack arrest at the next stitch line was also observed. This artifact was probably related to stitch line breakage indicating that steady-state was reached. This behaviour was quite obvious in the

case of low stitch density (4 stitch/cm²). However, in the case of high stitch density (12 stitch/cm²), this was not very obvious as the distance between the stitch lines decreased.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 12: The load versus displacement plot for (a) an unstitched ENF specimen and (b) for an ENF specimen stitched with 2-ply Kevlar thread at 12 st/cm².

After every crack growth step, the specimen was unloaded, the crack length marked, and the specimen was loaded again and the crack propagation load was determined. The complete R-curve was then determined using equation (5) from the load required for the crack to propagate at a known crack length. The out-of-plane shear modulus was estimated to be 5.8 GPa and the axial modulus was assumed to be same as the flexural modulus as the layup was essentially unidirectional. The R-curves are shown in Figure 13 where each specimen tested is marked by a different symbol. The mode II delamination toughness values, G_{IIRs} , are presented in Table 9. All values presented are the averages of 4-6 tests.

A comparison of the critical G_{IIC} values calculated for the unstitched specimens with the initiation G_{IIRi} values determined from the respective R-curves established a slight increase in toughness with the advent of stitching (Table 9). Typically, the R-curves (Figure 13) showed the establishment of a steady-state zone. The improvement was in excess of 100% when compared to the G_{IIC} of the unstitched specimens and closer to 200% for some of the higher

Fig. 13: R-curves determined for RTM specimens stitched with 2-ply Kevlar thread at (a) $4st/cm^2$, (b) $4st/cm^2$, discontinuous and (c) $12st/cm^2$. The R-curves for RTM specimens stitched with 3-ply and 4-ply Kevlar threads were similar.

stitch densities. However, to ensure the steady-state condition has been attained, it may be necessary to employ longer crack propagation lengths. The significant increase in toughness transpired mainly from the development of crack closure traction due to the bridging stitches. Increasing stitch density resulted in considerable improvement in G_{IIRs} . Increasing thread diameter also generated some improvement in G_{IIRs} (Table 9).

Micromechanical Model

The micromechanics-based theoretical model developed by Jain and Mai [2] has been employed to predict the improvement in mode II delamination toughness. The model assumes that the thread failure mechanism, as the crack propagates, consists of the elastic stretching of the stitches followed by rupture in the crack plane. The tensile strength of the stitching thread is assumed to be single-valued. To determine the load carried by the stitches, the frictional shear stress between the thread and the matrix is neglected and the load supported by each stitch is approximated from the elastic elongation of the thread. The energy release rate available for crack propagation is given by [2]:

$$G_{II} = \frac{A^*}{\cosh^2(\lambda\Delta a)} \left\{ \tau \left(\frac{\sinh(\lambda\Delta a)}{\lambda} + a_0 + \alpha h_c \right) - \frac{\lambda}{A^*} \left(\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} \right) \sinh(\lambda\Delta a) \right\}^2 \quad (7)$$

where τ is the shear stress and is related to the applied load P , α is the correction factor to include shear deformation, α_1 and α_2 are stitching parameters, and λ is related to material properties through A^* and α_1 . The expressions for τ , A^* , α , α_1 , α_2 , and λ may be found in Ref. [2]. Using the crack propagation condition, $G_{II} = G_{IIc}$, where G_{IIc} is the critical energy release rate for the unstitched composite, the shear stress τ required for crack propagation can be determined. Then the energy release rate from the applied load is calculated from:

$$G_{IIR} = A^* \tau^2 (a + \alpha h_c)^2 \quad (8)$$

With an increase in crack length a , the energy release rate increases and steady-state is attained when the stitches start breaking. The condition for steady-state attainment is

$$A^* \tau \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda^2} - \frac{1}{\lambda^2 \cosh(\lambda\Delta a)} + \frac{a_0}{\lambda} \tanh(\lambda\Delta a) \right\} + \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} \frac{1}{\cosh(\lambda\Delta a)} \geq \frac{\sigma_{fu} A_f (h_c + 0.5L_p)}{A_f E_f + F_t} \quad (9)$$

where σ_{fu} is the thread rupture strength.

The geometric and material parameters used to determine the effect of stitching on the mode II delamination toughness are given in Table 7. The energy release rate required to initiate the crack propagation in stitched laminates was taken to be that of the unstitched specimen, i.e. $G_{IIc} = 1.3 \text{ KJ/m}^2$. From SEM observation, it was found that breakage of the thread takes place in the crack plane rather than at the stitch loop on the surface. For this reason, the thread tensile strength, σ_{fu} , was taken as the stitched thread strength (Table 1).

Table 9: The mode II delamination toughness values determined experimentally.

RTM SPECIMEN	G_{IRI} (KJ/m ²)	G_{IRS} (KJ/m ²)	Improvement Factor
unstitched	1.29 ±0.10	--	--
2-ply K 4st/cm ²	1.45 ±0.02	2.98 ± 0.05	2.3
2-ply K 4st/cm ² (1)	1.76 ±0.10	2.30 ±0.05	1.8
2-ply K 8st/cm ²	1.50 ±0.05	3.62 ±0.03	2.8
2-ply K 12st/cm ²	1.51 ±0.09	4.10 ±0.05	3.2
3-ply K 4st/cm ²	1.43 ±0.04	3.06 ±0.06	2.4
4-ply K 4st/cm ²	1.52 ±0.03	3.14 ±0.10	2.4
4-ply K 8st/cm ²	1.61 ±0.11	3.70 ±0.09	2.9

K - Kevlar® thread and (1) - Discontinuous stitch

Fig. 14: Comparison of experimental results and theoretical predictions showing trend with stitch density for (a) 2-ply Kevlar thread and (b) 4-ply Kevlar thread.

The comparisons between experimental results and theoretical predictions are presented in Figures 14 and 15. In the case of 2-ply Kevlar (K40) thread, the correlation between theory and experiments was reasonable (see Figure 14a). However, in the case of 4-ply Kevlar (K80) thread, the theoretical predictions are higher than the experimental data. Similar trends were observed when we examined the effect of stitching on mode I delamination toughness. This ensures the accuracy of the model and, therefore, the discrepancies can be attributed to the inaccurate thread properties. The model can be further improved by using a more accurate force-displacement relationship for the thread in the composite instead of using a simple elastic constitutive law and by accounting for the effect of bending of stitches due to the relative slip of the top and bottom parts of the ENF specimen.

Fig. 15: Comparison of experimental results and theoretical predictions with Kevlar thread diameter at $4st/cm^2$.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been determined that the addition of through-thickness reinforcement in the form of stitches produces significant improvements in both mode I and mode II delamination toughness. The use of long aluminium tabs to prevent cantilever failure results in underestimation of the improvement in mode I delamination toughness. The correlation between theoretical predictions based on the models developed by Jain and Mai [1,2] and experimentally determined toughness was found to be good.

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